

Should we be using psychedelics or dissociatives to treat mental health conditions?

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General Introduction

Current and Controversial Issues in Biology (BIOL 700) is a seminar-style class at the University of New Hampshire.

The structure of the class is as follows: The class follows a repeating template of selecting a controversial issue proposed by UNH faculty members, finding 20 research papers on said topic, and encouraging the classroom to engage with and discuss the various papers selected for each topic. 3-4 days were allotted to reviewing and discussing each topic, with each topic of discussion being led by a group of 2-3 students in the class. 10 pro and 10 con papers were selected per topic, reviewed, and discussed. For each paper, three questions were asked about specific details of the article. One paper from each topic was chosen by each student, to thoroughly review the paper and prepare a short summary for the class to discuss, and answer the three questions. This allowed for more intensive understanding of the papers collectively, giving better insight into the topics at hand than if we had just read the abstract/Google search results. The class had an open discussion of each topic/paper, allowing thoughts on each paper to be shared. After reviewing all sources, the class was polled to form a stance on whether we collectively agreed we should enact the topic actions. The vote was on a scale of 1 to 10, with 1 indicating strong opposition to the controversial issue and 10 representing full support. The votes were averaged to determine the class's overall position on the topic.

Introduction

A growing population of individuals with treatment-resistant depression (TRD), post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and other mental health conditions have led researchers to begin investigating alternative therapies. These therapies include psychedelics and dissociatives, mainly focusing on the use of psilocybin and ketamine.

Psilocybin, a naturally occurring compound found in certain mushroom species, and ketamine, a synthetic dissociative anesthetic, have both demonstrated rapid-acting antidepressant effects in preliminary clinical trials (Goodwin et al., 2022; Gutierrez et al., 2024). These findings have helped to suggest a new path that psychiatric doctors can take in treatment planning where short-term pharmacological interventions could produce long-lasting changes in mood and cognition (Davis et al., 2021). In addition to their fast-acting antidepressant properties, psilocybin and ketamine therapies have shown some promise in improving overall emotional well-being, reducing anxiety, and enhancing cognitive flexibility (Yao et al., 2024). Recent studies have been expanded on these primarily findings, expanding to patients with neurodegenerative diseases, more specific types of depression, or PTSD (Back et al., 2024; Bradley et al., 2025; Dahan et al., 2024; Mario et al., 2025; Parikh et al., 2024).

Despite several studies displaying extremely positive results there are some concerns with the safety and efficacy of the use of such treatments for mental health.

Some systematic reviews and meta-analyses have concluded that the existing data doesn't suggest any excessive risk of misuse or harm (Dahan et al., 2024; Yao et al., 2024). However, some scholars have insisted that the research into psilocybin/ketamine therapy and its physiological action in the body is insufficient, and more research is necessary before being deemed safe for general use (Evans et al., 2025; Rhee et al., 2022). However other sources suggest that psychiatrists have overall hopeful and positive attitudes towards the potential benefits of psilocybin therapy (Gribben et al., 2024). Many articles have also sought to document the potential negative side effects and misuse potential of these drugs, in both clinical and recreational applications (Backman, 2023; Bremner et al., 2023; Short et al., 2018; Marrocu et al., 2024; Swainson et al., 2022; Szarmach et al., 2020; U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2023).

What are the pros?

Multiple clinical trials and meta-analyses suggest that psilocybin and ketamine therapies may be effective for individuals with treatment-resistant depression, major depressive disorder, and suicidal thoughts, particularly when traditional treatments have failed (Davis et al., 2021; Goodwin et al., 2022; Dahan et al., 2024). Both therapies have demonstrated rapid antidepressant effects, particularly in cases of treatment-resistant depression, and may reduce symptoms after only one or a few sessions (Gutierrez et al., 2024). Evidence has been coming out that also suggests these therapies may promote neuroplasticity. This could lead to longer-lasting improvements in mood, emotional regulation, and cognitive flexibility (Yao et al., 2024).

What are the cons?

Most of the cons of psilocybin and ketamine therapy stem from a limited understanding about their proper use. Because there has been such little research into these treatments thus far, there are many remaining questions about safety, efficacy, and appropriate use (Evans et al., 2025; Rhee et al., 2022). In particular, the mechanisms that allow psilocybin and ketamine to exert their therapeutic effects are not yet fully understood which makes it difficult to determine optimal dosing and patient selection. There is also limited evidence identifying which psychiatric disorders or patient populations may benefit most from these treatments, and there may be individuals at increased risk for worsened psychological outcomes following use (Marrocu et al., 2024). There is also much concern with misuse or abuse potential of these drugs, as both can be used recreationally. Recreational use of ketamine has become much more popular in the wake of researching its therapeutic uses, raising safety and regulatory concerns emphasized by both clinicians and public health agencies (Backman, 2023; Swainson et al., 2022; U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2023).

Pros of Psychedelic/Dissociative therapy	Sources	Cons of Psychedelic/Dissociative therapy	Sources
Potentially Effective in Treatment of: -Treatment Resistant Depression (TRD) -Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) -Suicidality -Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) -Substance Abuse Disorder -Parkinson's Disease (PD) -Alzheimer's Disease (AD)	Back et al., 2024 Bradley et al., 2025 Dahan et al., 2024 Davis et al., 2021 Goodwin et al., 2022 Gutierrez et al., 2024 Mario et al., 2025 Parikh et al., 2024 Yao et al., 2024	Insufficient Research	Evans et al., 2025 Rhee et al., 2022
		Potential for Negative Side Effects	Bremner et al., 2023 Short et al., 2018
		High Risk Treatment Groups	Marrocu et al., 2024 Szarmach et al., 2020
		Misuse/Abuse Potential	U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2023 Backman, 2023 Swainson et al., 2022

What do we think?

After reviewing these articles, we agree that while psilocybin and ketamine therapy have shown promising results in clinical trials, there is much more research to be done before these treatments should be made broadly available. Despite many clinical trials showing predominantly positive responses to treatment, sample sizes of such studies are exceptionally small and the amount of literature is simply insufficient at this point. There is also a lack of information about the physiological effects of these drugs on neurons. Understanding the action of treatments is an essential step in continuing research. The average vote of support in our class was ~5.7 after discussing the topic.

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